

A STUDY ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TECHNOSTRESS, ROLE STRESS AND PRODUCTIVITY IN THE SRI LANKAN BANKING SECTOR

Savindi Waduge¹, Nilantha Prasad²

¹*University of Sri Jayewardenepura, savindiwaduge7@gmail.com,*

²*University of Sri Jayewardenepura, nilantha@sjp.ac.lk*

Introduction

Modern Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) are becoming increasingly indispensable in almost every aspect of business. These ICTs expect constant renewal of technical skills and higher expectations for productivity from employees. Further when these ICTs get incorporated into work processes it makes employees endure pressure that exceed their capacity in terms of the level of difficulty or amount of work. This often leads to a condition known as technostress (Tarafdar et al., 2007; Wang, Shu & Tu, 2008).

Studies have found many implications of technology use in organizations and that they lead to effects that has a “dual nature” (Tarafdar et al., 2007). i.e., apart from causing major benefits, ICTs can also result in negative consequences.

There are very few past literatures which specifically focus on the negative implications on employees who are dependent on technology for their day-to-day work life in an organizational setting in Sri Lanka. Hence, this research is focusing on the stress created due to ICTs or technostress, and how it impacts productivity and role stress of employees in an organizational setting in the context of the role of banking employees in Sri Lanka.

From this study, the following objectives are expected to be achieved.

1. To identify the relationship between technostress and role stress

2. To identify the relationship between technostress and productivity
3. To identify the relationship between role stress and productivity

Literature Review

The research identifies that technostress can be studied in a broad context. Therefore, an approach frequently used in the literature to operationalize technostress by means of the measurement of the technostress creating factors introduced by Tarafdar et al. in 2007, namely, techno-overload, techno-invasion, techno-complexity, techno-security, and techno-uncertainty, is followed.

According to the role theory, role stress can result from inadequate or fear of inadequate performance, role overload, or role conflict (Turner & Turner, 2002). Studies show that role stress is mainly caused by role overload and role conflict in the workplace and computer-related technostress is positively related (Tarafdar et al., 2007).

This research also attempts to examine the relationship between technostress and ICT enabled productivity which is the extent to which ICT use enhances employee productivity (Zhao, Xia & Huang, 2020). Past literatures have arrived to the conclusion that some technostress creators have a positive effect on productivity, while others have a negative effect, therefore making the impact of different technostress creators is inconsistent. However, there are limits to employees effectively engaging in multitasking and other benefits introduced by ICTs and when these limits exceed, it causes strain. Failure to manage this strain induced by ICTs can offset expected increases in productivity (Lee, Lee & Suh, 2016).

Methodology

In this quantitative study, several methods are followed to empirically develop and validate the instrument for the constructs identified: Technostress, Role Stress and Productivity. Firstly, following the literature review, the measurements for the constructs are developed. The research

population are all the employees of commercial banks in Sri Lanka. Using simple convenience sampling technique, 92 responses were collected representing majority of commercial banks. To analyze the quantitative data, Smart PLS is used.

The relationships between the earlier mentioned constructs are explored in this study and the research model is analysed. The independent variable is technostress and the dependent variables are role stress and productivity.

Figure 3. Conceptual Model

The hypotheses of this study are,

H1: There is a positive relationship between technostress and role stress

H2: There is a negative relationship between technostress and productivity

H3: There is a negative relationship between role stress and productivity

Results

Descriptive statistics elaborate that majority in the sample consist of female employees. It is also observed that most of them were well educated. Sixty-five percent of the respondents had more than five years of work experience and more than fifty percent had worked in the organization for more than five years. This analysis indicates that most respondents had sufficient knowledge and were accustomed with their organizational work environment and related tasks.

To infer about the sample, a second order model is constructed. The constructs technostress and role stress are modeled as higher order constructs while their respective subconstructs are modeled as lower order constructs. Several similar empirical manuscripts have employed this hierarchical approach successfully (Maier et al., 2015; Tarafdar et al., 2007). To analyse and identify the relationship between technostress, role Stress and productivity, Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was used as it is more widely used among researchers in the area of study and a powerful statistical technique that is used to measure the causal relationships between variables.

Figure 2. Research model with outer loadings and R2 values

Indicator reliability, construct reliability and convergent validity is established in this study using appropriate and validated methods.

Hypothesis testing is done using bootstrapping which estimated the path coefficients, T statistics and P values using 500 subsamples at 0.95 confidence level.

Table 3. Hypothesis and P values

	Relationship	Path Coefficients	T Statistics	P Values	Supported/ Unsupported
H1	Technostress -> Role Stress	0.923	48.054	0	Supported
H2	Technostress -> Productivity	-1.046	4.332	0	Supported
H3	Role Stress -> Productivity	0.639	2.539	0.011	Supported

According to the context of the study and based on a ninety-five percent confidence level, H1, H2 and H3 are supported. However, although H3 is significant, it is a positive support which means that role stress has a positive effect on productivity.

Discussion

This paper describes and empirically elaborates the link between technostress and role stress. This relationship further establishes the impact that is created by the stress due to excessive use of technology towards organizational roles and structure by suggesting that it can deepen the existing levels of stress due to aspects of the individual's role.

Next, the research explains that productivity and technostress are negatively related. This analysis shows support to the concept of information technology productivity paradox which is debated upon by numerous researchers. The concept states that increase in the investment of ICTs can have negative effects on productivity in an organization (Hajli, Sims & Ibragimov, 2015).

Finally, the study explains that there is a significant positive relationship between role stress and productivity. This is not the typical conclusion formed by previous literature which had assessed the relationship between role stress and productivity. However, this could have implications on the

concept of eustress which is the positive perception of a stressful situation (Califf et al., 2015).

Conclusion

The relationships identified in this research open opportunities for further studies about the organizational effects of technostress.

The weaknesses of the study identified below could be overcome by future research work.

1. The study is limited to a quantitative analysis.
2. The study cannot be limited by concluding that technostress negatively impacts productivity. There could be other factors impacting productivity in an organizational setting.
3. This research focuses on only banking employees so it could be argued that this group is not necessarily representative of all organizational workers.

It is hoped that the interpretations of this study would provide important comprehension and would be beneficial to organizations who refer this research in managing workplace stress, especially stress created due to technology usage, to reap the real benefits of ICT adaptation.

References

Califf, C., Sarker S. and Fitzgerald C. (2015) 'The Bright and Dark Sides of Technostress: An Empirical Study of Healthcare', *International Conference on Information Systems*.

Hajli, M., Sims, J. M. and Ibragimov, V. (2015) 'Information technology (IT) productivity paradox in the 21st century', *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*.

Lee, S. B., Lee, S. C. and Suh, Y. H. (2016) 'Technostress from mobile communication and its impact on quality of life and productivity', *Total*

Quality Management & Business Excellence, pp. 1 – 16.

Maier, C., Laumer S., Weinert C., and Weitzel T. (2015) 'The Effects of Technostress and Switching-stress on Discontinued Use of Social Networking Services: A Study of Facebook Use', *Information Systems Journal*.

Ralph H. Turner (2001) 'Role Theory', in Jonathan H. Turner (ed.) *Handbook of Sociological Theory*. University of California: Springer, pp. 233-254.

Tarafdar, M. *et al.* (2007) 'The impact of technostress on role stress and productivity', *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 24(1), pp. 301–328.

Wang, K., Shu, Q. and Tu, Q. (2008) 'Technostress under different organizational environments: An empirical investigation', *Computers in Human Behavior*, 24(6), pp. 3002–3013.

Zhao, X., Xia, Q., and Wayne, W. H. (2020). 'Impact of technostress on productivity from the theoretical perspective of appraisal and coping processes', *Information & Management*, 57(8).